

HEAT CALCULATION OF THE CONCENTRATOR OF THE HELIOPYROLISIS DEVICE

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Abstract. Reducing energy consumption in pyrolysis technology is one of the main problems. Because initially energy (heat) must be supplied to ensure the temperature regime of the reactor. Decomposition of biomass waste requires a lot of thermal energy, and additional heating of biomass requires excessive energy consumption. Usually, the processes carried out in a pyrolysis plant are carried out at the expense of coal, natural gas or electricity.

Key words: heliopyrolysis, concentrator, pyrolysis reactor, biomass, amount of heat, solar radiation, thermal efficiency, alternative fuel, temperature, time.

Introduction

The problem of reducing energy consumption in biomass pyrolysis can be solved by using a heliothermic heating system. As a result of the research conducted in this field, a method of using solar concentrators in the biomass pyrolysis process, i.e. heliopyrolysis method, was proposed (Fig. 1)[1].

Figure 1. The principle scheme of the heliopyrolysis device.

A heliopyrolysis device based on a solar concentrator is environmentally friendly and reduces energy consumption for the process. The temperature required for the process is generated by parabolic cylindrical solar concentrators. The advantages of the proposed method are that the pyrolysis reactor can be continuously heated by solar energy using solar concentrators. The heat supplied to the reactor by the steam-cylinder solar concentrators is determined by the heat calculation of the existing device.

Materials and methods

A parabolic cylindrical concentrator has a reflecting surface, and a beam of length l is received along its axis the location of the reactor is narrow (Fig. 2). The axis of the concentrator is located in the east-west direction, and the mirror is automatically directed to the sun. The screen installed on the collector serves to reduce heat loss [2,3,4].

Figure 2. Scheme of a parabolic cylindrical concentrator.

A - overview; B - cross section; 1 – parabolic cylindrical mirror; 2 – screen; 3rd reactor; NS - north-south; E -W – east- west.

In the heliopyrolysis reactor [5-20]:

$$Q_{yut} = R kl DS_{\perp}; \quad (1)$$

where: R is the reflection coefficient of mirror; k - heat transfer coefficient; $l D$ - radiation surface, m^2 ; $S_{\perp}$ - unit of solar radiation falling on the surface, W/m^2

If we do not take into account convective heat losses, the reactor loses energy in those parts that are not protected by the insulation layer. Heat losses by radiation are determined by the following equation [20-25]:

$$Q_{iq} = e s T_p^4 2 p r l (1 - g / p); \quad (2)$$

where: e – radiation capacity; $s = 5.67 \times 10^{-8} W/(m^2 K^4)$ - Stefan-Bolsman constant; T_p – reactor temperature, K; r is the radius of reactor tube i, m.

In order to reduce heat losses, the radius r should be reduced, and in order to increase the energy Q , the size of the reactor pipe should match the size of the concentrator:

$$r = \lambda th; \theta = R_o / L_o; \quad (3)$$

where: R_o is the solar radius; L_o - distance between the earth and the sun, km.

The heliopyrolysis reactor pipe is determined by the following formula:

$$T_n = \left[\frac{kR \tau_s S_{\perp} \cos \tau^o}{\varepsilon \sigma} \right]^{1/4} \left[\frac{D}{2\pi(1 - \gamma / \pi)} \right]^{1/4}; \quad (4)$$

where: t_k is the light absorption coefficient of the surface.

The temperature will be maximum. In this case, the second term in equation (4) tends to $1/\theta$. In this case, the maximum temperature of the reactor-tube is as follows [26-28]:

$$T_{n\max} = \left[\frac{kR\tau_k S_{\perp} \cos \tau^{\circ}}{\varepsilon\sigma\theta} \right]^{1/4} \quad (5)$$

inside the heliopyrolysis reactor is determined by the following equation:

$$T_p^4 k Q_{reak} = Q_{yut} - Q_f < Q_y; \quad (6)$$

where: Q_f is the useful heat obtained from the heat carrier, W.

Results and discussion

Usually, the heating temperature in such reactors is $300 \div 450$ °C. Under favorable conditions, the heat carrier can heat up to 700 °C.

The surface of the concentrator surface is called the aperture $F_k = lD$. The concentration coefficient X is determined by the ratio of the aperture on the heat-receiving surface F_p to the surface:

$$X = F_k / F_p = S_p / S_{\perp}; \quad (7)$$

where: S_p is the average radiation of the receiver surface.

Figure 3. Concentration coefficient X and heat sink temperature

The ratio between t_t (°C).

- 1) Lower limit when $Q_{yut} = Q_{tp}$; 2) when $\eta = 40\%$; 3) when $\eta = 60\%$

Conclusion

In normal conditions $S_{\perp} = 800$ W/m²; $R = 0.8$; $k_t = 1$; The maximum temperature $T_{p\max} = 750$ K is reached when $\theta = 4.6 \times 10^{-3}$ rad. Therefore, it is possible to create a temperature in the reactor that ensures the pyrolysis mode through the calculation concentrator, and heat energy is saved for private needs.

REFERENCES

1. D.S. Strebkov, E.V. Tveryanovich. Koncentratory solnechnogo izlucheniya / Pod ed. Academician RASHN D.S. Strebkova. - M.: GNU VIESX, 2007. - 316 p.
2. Zakhidov R.A., Umarov G.Ya., Weiner A.A. Theory and calculation of helio-technical concentrator system. Tashkent: FAN, 1977.
3. Hongfei Zheng. Solar Energy Desalination Technology. Elsevier, 2017. pp 784.
4. Uzakov G.N., Novik A.V., Davlonov X.A., Almardanov X.A., Chuliev S.E. Heat and Material Balance of Heliopyrolysis Device. ENERGETIKA. Proceedings of CIS higher education institutions and power engineering associations. 2023; 66(1):57-65. <https://doi.org/10.21122/1029-7448-2023-66-1-57-65>
5. Uzakov, G.N., Almardanov, X.A., Kodirov, I.N., Aliyarova, L.A. Studying the temperature regime of the heliopyrolysis device reactor. E3S Web of Conferences, 2023, 411, 01040 DOI: 10.1051/e3sconf/202341101040
6. X. Davlonov, Study on heat and material balance of heliopyrolysis device, AIP Conference Proceedings, 2686, 020023 (2022)
7. Almardanov, X. A., et al. "Application of solar concentrators to obtain alternative fuel through a heliopyrolysis device."Universum: Technical Sciences 3 (2021): 8-12.
8. Almardanov, H. and Chuliyev, S. 2022. Biomassadan geliopiroliz usulida yoqilg'i olish tajriba qurilmasining parametrlarini asoslash. Innovatsion texnologiyalar. 1, 4 (Nov. 2022), 92–96.
9. Davlonov, X. A., X. A. Almardanov, and I. A. Khatamov. "A program for modeling and calculating the exergic balance of a heliopyrolysis device to obtain alternative fuels from biomass." No DGU 10337 (2021).
10. Almardanov, H. A. (2023). Calculation of the energy efficiency of the solar concentrator heliopyrolysis device. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(12), 147–150.
11. Sh.B. Imomov, X.A. Alimardonov. Heat mode solar heating systems based on flat reflectors, sets on the north side of the building. Молодой ученый, 2015, 335-336 ст.
12. Davlonov X.A., Almardanov H.A., Toshboyev A.R., Umirov F.B. Method of Thermal Processing of Biomass With Heliopyrolysis Device. 2021, International Journal of Human Computing Studies, 3(2), 149-151.
13. Алмарданов Х.А., Хатамов И.А. Тураев З.Б., Юсупов Р.Э., Эшонкулов М.Н., Жовлиев С.М., Применение солнечных концентраторов для приема альтернативного топлива через устройство гелиопиролиза // Universum:

технические науки. – 2021, Март. –№. 3(84). С. 8-11.
<https://7universum.com/ru/tech/archive/item/11381>

14. Давлонов Х.А., Алмарданов Х.А., Гадоев С.А., Шаймарданов И.З. Исследование теплового режима процесса гелиопиролиза биомасса // Универсум: технические науки: электрон. научн. журн. 2021. 4(85) 5-8 ст.
<https://7universum.com/ru/tech/archive/item/11550>

15. Узаков Г.Н., Новик А.В., Давлонов Х.А., Алмарданов Х.А., Чулиев С.Э. Тепловой и материальный баланс гелиопиролизного устройства. Энергетика. Известия высших учебных заведений и энергетических объединений СНГ. 2023;66(1):57-65. <https://doi.org/10.21122/1029-7448-2023-66-1-57-65>

16. Т.Я. Хамраев, Х.А. Алмарданов. Режим работы установок для получения биогаза из сельскохозяйственных отходов. Молодой ученый. — 2020. — № 25 (315). — С. 49-52.

17. К.К. Рахимова, Х.А. Алмарданов, С.И. Хамраев, С.М. Шамуратова, А.Р. Тошбоев, Э.Э. Турдиев. Теплоснабжение и энергосбережение сельскохозяйственных сооружений с пассивной системой солнечного отопления. ГГТУ им. ПО Сухого, 2020, 242-245 ст.

18. Almardanov , X. (2023). Research of heat exchange processes in the reactor of the solar concentrator heliopyrolysis device. Muqobil Energetika, 2(01), 41–47.

19. Almardanov H.A., Uzakov G.N. 2023. Technical-Economic Justification Of The Efficiency Of Using The Heliopyrolysis Device In Heliothermic Processing Of Biomass. Eurasian Journal of Engineering and Technology. 23, (Oct. 2023), 6–11.

20. Allamuratovich, Davlonov X., et al. "Method of Thermal Processing of Biomass with Heliopyrolysis Device." International Journal of Human Computing Studies, vol. 3, no. 2, 2021, pp. 149-151, doi:10.31149/ijhcs.v3i2.1574.

21. Саматова Ш. Й. и др. Экономичные и энергосберегающие электрические приборы //Современные проблемы и перспективы развития агропромышленного комплекса. – 2021. – С. 117-120.

22. Almardanov , H. A. (2023). Calculation of the energy efficiency of the solar concentrator heliopyrolysis device. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(12), 147–150.

23. Ғ.Н. Узаков, Ҳ.А. Алмарданов. Параболик қуёш концентраторли гелиопиролиз қурилмасининг иссиқлик-технологик режимини тадқиқ қилиш. International Conference “Fundamental and Applied Problems of Modern Physics”, October 19-21, 2023, 123-128 b.

24. G.N. Uzakov, X.A. Almardanov, I.N. Kodirov, L.A. Aliyarova. Modeling the heat balance of a solar concentrator heliopyrolysis device reactor. BIO Web Conf., 71 (2023) 01098. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1051/bioconf/20237101098>

25. Almardanov, X. (2023). Study of the temperature regime of the heliopyrolysis device with a parabolic concentrator. *Innovatsion Texnologiyalar*, 51(03), 33–39.

26. Uzakov, G., Almardanov, H. (2023). Parabolik quyosh konsentratorli geliopiroliz qurilmasining texnik-iqtisodiy parametrlarini asoslash. *Muqobil Energetika*, 1(10), 50–56.

27. Almardanov H.A., Uzakov G.N. Technical-Economic Justification Of The Efficiency Of Using The Heliopyrolysis Device In Heliothermic Processing Of Biomass. *Genius Repository*. 23, (Oct. 2023), 6–11.

28. Almardanov , X. (2023). Research of heat exchange processes in the reactor of the solar concentrator heliopyrolysis device. *Muqobil Energetika*, 2(01), 41–47.